

STONE MONUMENT ENSEMBLES AND THE CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT

Project ID: 101098422

MILESTONE 5

ON-SITE DIGITAL ACQUISITIONS

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MILESTONE 5 – ON-SITE DIGITAL ACQUISITIONS

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

On-site digital acquisitions	1
Milestone 5 –	2
Executive Summary	Error! Bookmark not defined.
1. Acquisition reports	6
1.1 Hundskirche, Austria 2024	7
1.2 Žugića Bare, Montenegro 2024	10
1.3 Ravanjska Vrata (Kupres), Radimlja (Stolac), Blidinje (Dugo Polje) – Bosnia and Herzegovina 2024	13
1.4 Crljivica necropolis (Cista velika), Museum of Croatian Archaeological Monuments (Split) – Croatia 2025	17
1.5 Kopošići Necropolis, Križevići Necropolis and the National Museum (Sarajevo) – Bosnia and Herzegovina 2025	20
1.6 Cimetière Saint Jean (Caen), France 2025	25
1.7 Mramorje (Perućac), Serbia 2025	27
1.8 Domvs Romana (Rabat), Malta 2025	29
1.9 Unsleben, Kleinbardorf, Germany 2025	32
Outlook	36
Appendix	37
Appendix 1.1 Hundskirche, Austria	38
Appendix 1.2 Žugića Bare, Montenegro	40
Appendix 1.3 Ravanjska Vrata (Kupres), Radimlja (Stolac), Blidinje (Dugo Polje) – Bosnia and Herzegovina	48
Appendix 1.4 Crljivica necropolis (Cista velika), Museum of Croatian Archaeological Monuments (Split) – Croatia	56
Appendix 1.5 Kopošići Necropolis, Križevići Necropolis and the National Museum (Sarajevo) – Bosnia and Herzegovina	61
Appendix 1.6 Cimetière Saint Jean, France	66
Appendix 1.7 Mramorje, Serbia	68
Appendix 1.8 Domvs Romana, Malta	70
Appendix 1.9 Unsleben, Kleinbardorf (Germany)	72

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As part of Work Package 4 (WP4) of the STECCI project, a comprehensive programme of digital acquisition was carried out to document Stećci cultural heritage sites and selected monuments across Europe. The objective of this effort was to generate accurate and high-resolution 3D datasets that will serve as the basis for preservation, research, education, and dissemination activities within the wider framework of European cultural heritage.

Between July 2024 and August 2025, nine fieldwork campaigns were undertaken in collaboration with local partners, covering fifteen sites across eight countries. The sites included necropolises, museums, and heritage landscapes, representing a diverse cross-section of Stećci contexts. Each mission combined planning with on-site reconnaissance to ensure that acquisition methodologies were adapted to site-specific conditions.

The acquisition campaign employed a range of advanced digitisation techniques, including aerial photogrammetry with UAVs, terrestrial and hand-held photogrammetry, terrestrial LiDAR scanning, and, where appropriate, Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) for fine surface details. In addition, low-cost digitisation trials were conducted to support Task 4.3, and 360° photography and videography were captured to contribute to dissemination and immersive interpretation under Task 4.4.

All designated sites and selected monuments were successfully recorded, with data acquisition tailored to monument typology, accessibility, and environmental conditions. In total, the milestone generated a foundational dataset of raw 3D acquisitions that will be processed into finalised models for use in conservation monitoring, educational tools, and public engagement platforms.

This milestone report documents the achievement of Milestone 5: On-Site Digital Acquisitions. It provides both a high-level overview of the acquisition campaign and detailed, site-by-site reports outlining fieldwork activities, team composition, applied methodologies, and encountered constraints. The results confirm the successful completion of the physical acquisition phase, laying the groundwork for the subsequent post-processing and asset production tasks that will continue up to Month 36, culminating in Milestone 6 with the dissemination of the fully processed digital assets on the STECCI platform.

1. ACQUISITION REPORTS

The acquisition campaign was structured as a series of coordinated fieldwork operations across eight countries, covering fifteen distinct Stećci sites and associated museum collections (Table 1). This section presents the operational detail of that campaign, providing a breakdown of activities carried out at each site and highlighting the practical implementation of methodologies in diverse environmental and logistical contexts.

Table 1. The Digital Acquisition field work conducted as part of WP4, Task 4.1

No.	Destination	Site/s	Date	On-site Partner
1	Austria	“Hundskirche”, Paternion	1 st -3 rd July 2024	HM, UAA
2	Montenegro	Necropolis in Zugica Bare	7 th -11 th August 2024	HM, UDG
3	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Ravanjska Vrata (Kupres), Radimlja (Stolac), Dugo Polje (Blidinje)	16 th -21 st September 2024	HM, UNSA
4	Croatia	Crljivica necropolis (Cista Velika) and the Split Museum	28 th April -2 nd May 2025	HM, UMAS
5	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Kopošići Necropolis, Križevići Necropolis and the National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Sarajevo)	25 th -30 th May 2025	HM, UNSA, QAB
6	France	Cimetière Saint Jean (Caen)	17 th -20 th June 2025	HM, IMT
7	Serbia	Mramorje (Perućac)	15 th -18 th July 2025	HM, UNSPMF
8	Malta	Domvs Romana (Rabat)	22 nd -31 st July 2025	HM
9	Germany	Unsleben, Kleinbardorf	4 th -8 th Aug 2025	HM, SPK

Across sites, acquisition strategies were adapted pragmatically, with teams deploying different combinations of technologies in response to local conditions. These included aerial photogrammetry (drone-based), terrestrial and hand-held photogrammetry, and terrestrial LiDAR scanning. Where appropriate, Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI) was also employed to capture fine epigraphic and decorative details.

The following subsections provide site-by-site reports, documenting the fieldwork process, encountered constraints, and the raw acquisition outputs secured during each campaigns. Collectively, these records confirm that all designated sites and priority monuments were successfully acquired, forming a complete dataset for subsequent post-processing and integration into STECCI’s dissemination and conservation workflows.

1.1 HUNDSKIRCHE, AUSTRIA 2024

HM Acquisition Team: Francesco Vella (Photogrammetry Specialist and LiDAR Operator), Jacob Saliba (Photogrammetry Specialist and RTI Operator), Anthony Cassar (Head of Technology and Experience Development)

On-site Partners: (UAA) Marija Milchin, Christoph Schlessmann

Site Name: Hundskirche Kreuzen

Date and Timeframe of Acquisition: 2nd July 2024

Overview of 3D Scanned Assets

The "Hundskirche" is a historical site in Carinthia, Austria, consisting of a limestone rock formation used as a secret Protestant worship site during the Counter-Reformation in the 17th and 18th centuries. The site features engravings of dogs, religious symbols, and inscriptions. The name "Hundskirche" (Dog's Church) references the dog's depiction, symbolising Protestant resistance. Today, it is part of the "Path of the Book," a trail commemorating Protestant heritage.

Location/Environment Details

The monument site was set in a dense, forested area with limited road access, making it challenging to transport equipment. A nearby stream added to the complexity, as the team had to carry the equipment across it. The terrain was uneven, with natural features like slopes and rocks, complicating the setup of scanning equipment, particularly for RTI scans. The surfaces of the stone were dark and covered in moss, which made them slippery, shiny, and reflective due to moisture. This required extra care in adjusting lighting and exposure settings to capture detailed scans. The proximity of some graffiti to the stream further complicated the work, forcing the team to maintain distance for certain LiDAR scans while needing to wade into the water for photogrammetry captures. Additionally, the natural light conditions were inconsistent, with the team needing to manage shading and blocking light, especially when working in awkward, uneven spots. The overall environment was both physically demanding and technically challenging, requiring careful planning and adaptability.

Methodologies

- Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR)
- Terrestrial Photogrammetry
- Reflectance Transformation Imaging (RTI)

LiDAR and photogrammetry were both used for 3D scanning, often employed together to minimise risk and ensure accuracy. With photogrammetry, there was uncertainty about whether the scanned images would successfully generate a 3D model, especially when dealing with large or unique objects. However, using LiDAR alongside photogrammetry ensured that the images had a reliable reference for alignment, as LiDAR data could be monitored in real time. Additionally, LiDAR was crucial for providing dimensional accuracy to the scan. RTI (Reflectance Transformation Imaging) was also employed and was strongly suggested by UAA partner Christoph Schlessmann as the ideal methodology in this case due to the prioritisation and need to analyse the depth and level of degradation of the graffiti engraved in the monument.

Process

Graffiti 1

The team performed two rounds of scanning using both LiDAR and photogrammetry. In the first scan, they used the photogrammetry rig/flash and LiDAR together, incorporating four targets to aid in merging the data during post-processing. For the second scan, the photogrammetry rig was not used, and six targets were employed instead of four to create more contrasting reference points for the alignment software, Reality Capture, in post-processing. This adjustment aimed to improve the accuracy of the data integration.

For this graffiti the team also used the RTI, which will result in three detailed scans. The process required meticulous setup due to the uneven terrain surrounding the graffiti, which made positioning the tripod a challenge. The team worked collaboratively to overcome these obstacles, successfully blocking out ambient light to capture the best possible images. With the help of the UAA project partners, they managed to stabilise the tripod and optimise the setup despite the natural difficulties presented by the environment. This careful attention to detail ensured that the RTI scans provided high-quality data, enhancing the overall digital representation of the cultural heritage present at the site.

Graffiti 2

Scanning the second graffiti proved to be more challenging due to its proximity to a stream. As a result, the LiDAR data was captured from a distance of approximately 5 meters. For the photogrammetry process, several images were taken from this distance; however, the team also captured an additional set of images from a closer range to the graffiti. This dual approach aimed to enhance the detail and accuracy of the digital representation.

Difficulties/Constraints during Acquisition

During the scanning process, aside from the environmental challenges discussed in the location details section, the team encountered challenges with Wi-Fi connectivity, due to the remote location, between the LiDAR device and the tablet, which required some effort to adjust and resolve.

Fig. 1: “Hundskirche”

Fig. 2: Graffiti 1

Fig. 3: Graffiti 2

Fig. 4,5,6: On-site work in progress; Terrestrial Photogrammetry, RTI and LiDAR set-up

1.2 ŽUGIĆA BARE, MONTENEGRO 2024

HM Acquisition Team: Francesco Vella (LiDAR Operator), Jacob Saliba (Photogrammetry Specialist), and Aaron Edward Cole (Drone Pilot).

On-site Partners: (UDG) Aleksandra Gogic, Vedran Pean

Site Name: Žugića Bare

Date and Timeframe of Acquisition:

Area 1:

- First Scan – 8th August 2024
- Second Scan – 10th August 2024

Area 2:

- 9th August 2024

Area 1

Overview of 3D Scanned Assets

Žugića Bare, a village 7 km southeast of Žabljak on Mount Durmitor's plateau, hosts one of Montenegro's largest necropolises, with nearly 300 stećci dating to the 14th–15th centuries and listed as UNESCO World Heritage. Most are uncarved or roughly carved, arranged in west–east rows, with decorated examples featuring crosses, bows, swords, and rare scenes such as dancers, a rider on a deer, and unique architectural forms. Weathering has obscured many motifs, but surviving carvings provide insight into medieval funerary traditions.

Location/Environment Details

The site is situated in an open area that is readily accessible to the public and is frequently visited by tourists. While the terrain is generally flat and straightforward to navigate, the high volume of visitors posed a challenge to uninterrupted scanning operations and created potential risks, such as the accidental movement of alignment targets. The environmental conditions during the campaign were characterised by humid weather and occasional gusts of wind, which affected drone stability. Additionally, several tombstones showed advanced weathering, with some partially obscured by overgrown vegetation.

Methodologies

- Light Detection and Ranging
- Terrestrial Photogrammetry
- Aerial Photogrammetry

The acquisition strategy employed a combination of aerial photogrammetry, ground-based photogrammetry, and LiDAR scanning. Drone photogrammetry was used to document the overall layout and spatial context of the necropolis, while LiDAR ensured dimensional accuracy, particularly for individual Stećci. Photogrammetry rigs were deployed for selected monuments to achieve higher-resolution surface detail.

Process

Prior to scanning, targets were distributed across the site, with higher concentrations placed near seven Stećci identified in consultation with the site partners (UDG) for detailed recording. The drone pilot began with an automated aerial photogrammetry sequence covering the entire site, while other team members simultaneously performed LiDAR and ground-based photogrammetry

of the prioritised monuments. Additional drone passes were then conducted manually to refine coverage and avoid capturing team members in the images.

For the ground-based component, two capture strategies were employed. The first involved systematic grid-pattern photography, moving in straight lines across the site, and the second applied a 360-degree spherical capture method from fixed points to generate panoramic image sets. These datasets complemented the aerial imagery, enriching the final site model.

Upon reviewing the data collected later that day, the team identified an issue: the automated drone images were of insufficient quality for reliable alignment in Reality Capture, while manually captured drone images had a higher resolution. Given the contingency day available, a second scan of the site was conducted, following the same acquisition methodology but with key refinements. The improved approach included a greater number of manually captured drone images, earlier start times to minimise tourist interference, and enhanced resolution for individual tombstone scans. Data verification following the second scan confirmed that the captured material met the required quality standards.

Total scanned monuments: 7

Difficulties/Constraints during Acquisition

The primary challenge at Area 1 was the persistent interference from tourist activity, particularly during the first scan. This occasionally caused delays and introduced the risk of displaced targets. Although starting earlier on the contingency day reduced the impact of visitors, minor disruptions persisted. Technical challenges included a brief drone malfunction that affected part of the image dataset, though this was mitigated by redundant capture strategies.

Area 2

Overview of 3D Scanned Assets

The second area of the necropolis contains a smaller number of tombstones, similar in stylistic execution to those at Area 1 but more isolated in placement. These monuments, also bearing medieval carvings, are of significant historical value and form part of the same UNESCO inscription.

Location/Environment Details

This site's secluded position made it less susceptible to tourist interference but more challenging to access. The terrain was uneven, with rocks and dense vegetation complicating equipment placement. Afternoon weather conditions began to deteriorate, with approaching thunderstorms posing a potential threat to both the workflow and the safety of equipment.

Methodologies

The same combined methodology was applied here as at Area 1: aerial and ground-based photogrammetry complemented by LiDAR scanning. Drones were particularly valuable in this location for efficiently covering the area, given the uneven ground conditions that made manual scanning more physically demanding.

Process

The refined workflow developed during the second scan of area 1 was implemented in the area 2, including more frequent placement of alignment targets due to the smaller spatial footprint of the site. This ensured improved model alignment during processing. Aerial coverage was completed swiftly, followed by detailed ground-based captures of the individual monuments. The reduced size

of the site allowed for efficient completion of all planned scans within the allocated timeframe, despite the onset of adverse weather.

Total scanned monuments: 8

Difficulties/Constraints during Acquisition

The primary constraints were environmental rather than human. The rocky and vegetated terrain required manual adjustment of scanning setups, and deteriorating weather limited operational time in the latter part of the session. A small number of visitors were present but could be managed effectively due to the contained layout of the site.

Fig. 7: Area 1: Žugića Bare

Fig. 8: Area 2: Žugića Bare

Fig. 9,10,11: On-site work in progress; LiDAR, terrestrial and aerial photogrammetry set-up

1.3 RAVANJSKA VRATA (KUPRES), RADIMLJA (STOLAC), BLIDINJE (DUGO POLJE) – BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA 2024

HM Acquisition Team: Francesco Vella (Photogrammetry Specialist), Jacob Saliba (Photogrammetry Specialist), Aaron Edward Cole (Drone Pilot), Myron Saliba (LiDAR Operator)

On-site Partners: (UNSA) Nusret Dreskovic, Saida Ibragic, Edin Bujak

Dates of Acquisition: 16th – 21st September 2024

Site Name: Blidinje, Dugo Polje

Date: 17th September 2024

Site Description:

Blidinje, a karst plateau in northern Herzegovina between the Čvrstica, Muharica, and Vran mountains, is part of a nature park centred on Dugo polje. Known for Blidinje Lake and rich biodiversity, the area has a long history of human habitation, with prehistoric, Roman, and medieval remains. The Dugo polje necropolis, the largest in Blidinje, contains 150 stećci, mostly slabs and chests dating to the 14th–15th centuries. Thirty-two bear decorations, with gabled roofs and chests showing the finest craftsmanship. Arranged in southwest–northeast rows, the site is well-preserved following recent conservation and is inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage list.

Location and Environment:

The site is characterised by mild slopes and grassy terrain, facilitating drone flights and LiDAR scans. Weather conditions were optimal with clear visibility and low wind, supporting accurate data capture.

Methodologies:

- Aerial Photogrammetry (automated and manual flights)
- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- Terrestrial LiDAR scanning

Photogrammetry was employed to capture the site's layout and Stećci details, while LiDAR provided high-precision measurements of the monuments' dimensions.

Process:

Targets were placed strategically around the site, with closer positioning around priority monuments identified in collaboration with UNSA partners. An automated drone flight surveyed the entire site, followed by ground-based detailed scans and LiDAR setups. Manual aerial photography supplemented automated captures, focusing on priority areas.

Total scanned monuments: 8

Difficulties/Constraints:

None.

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Site Name: Ravanska Vrata, Kupres

Date: 18th September 2024

Site Description:

Kupres, in western Bosnia, comprises four fields surrounded by mountains, with evidence of long-term settlement. The area hosts over 1,000 stećci across 40+ necropolises, mainly slabs and chests, often located near old roads or prehistoric tumuli. The most notable is the UNESCO-listed Ravanjska vrata necropolis, a historic passage between the Vukovsko and Ravanjsko fields. It consists of an Upper and Lower necropolis: the Lower holds 43 stećci, including decorated slabs, chests, and gabled roofs, while the Upper contains 25 with motifs such as rosettes and tournament scenes. Ravanska Vrata featured fewer Stećci than Blidinje, situated on uneven, hilly terrain with scattered monuments.

Location and Environment:

The hilly and rocky ground made transport of equipment and setup tricky. A road divides the site into two parts: one with significant monuments and one with scattered stones. Weather was stable, though rain was forecast, prompting schedule adjustments.

Methodologies:

- Aerial Photogrammetry
- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- Terrestrial LiDAR
- Additional testing of low-cost scanning technology (PolyCam)

Photogrammetry was employed to capture the site's layout and Stećci details, while LiDAR provided high-precision measurements of the tombstones' dimensions.

Process:

The workflow mirrored that of Blidinje, with additional testing of cost-effective alternatives. Target placement and scanning focused on accessible areas with priority tombstones.

Total scanned monuments: 5

Difficulties/Constraints:

Rough terrain limited access to some areas, but no priority monuments were located in inaccessible zones.

Site Name: Radimlja, Stolac

Date: 20th September 2024

Site Description:

Radimlja, located in Vidovo polje near Stolac, contains 133 stećci, of which 63 are decorated with a wide range of motifs. Its most iconic carving depicts a male figure with an uplifted hand, often interpreted as a warrior, alongside weapons, round dances, animals, and hunting scenes. Five Bosnian Cyrillic epitaphs link the necropolis to the 15th-century Vlach katun of Miloradović Hrabren, naming leaders such as Duke Stipan (d. 1470) and Duke Petar (1477). Celebrated as the most famous stećci site and listed by UNESCO, Radimlja is renowned for its artistry and historical significance.

Location and Environment:

The terrain is mostly flat, facilitating drone and LiDAR operations. Recent heavy rain left the soil damp but dry enough for scanning. A road dissects the site, with frequent traffic creating scanning challenges near the fence and road edges.

Methodologies:

- Aerial Photogrammetry
- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- Terrestrial LiDAR

Photogrammetry was employed to capture the site's layout and stećci details, while LiDAR provided high-precision measurements of the tombstones' dimensions.

Process:

The data acquisition process followed established protocols. The site's accessibility resulted in occasional tourist interruptions. Detailed scanning was difficult near the road and fence, but UNSA partners indicated this area's monuments are of less priority within the scope of the digital acquisition.

Total scanned monuments: 7

Difficulties/Constraints:

Tourist presence and proximity to infrastructure limited scanning options in parts of the site.

Fig. 12: Blindinje (Site 1); LiDAR set-up

Fig. 13: Ravanjska Vrata (Site 2)

Fig. 14: Radimlja (Site 3); On-site work in progress

1.4 CRLJIVICA NECROPOLIS (CISTA VELIKA), MUSEUM OF CROATIAN ARCHAEOLOGICAL MONUMENTS (SPLIT) – CROATIA 2025

HM Acquisition Team: Warren Attard (Photogrammetry Specialist), Kyle Attard (Photogrammetry Specialist), Aaron Edward Cole (Drone Pilot)

On-site Partners: (UMAS) Siniša Bizjak, Krešimir Bosnić

Dates of Acquisition: 29th – 30th April 2025

Site 1: Museum of Croatian Archaeological Monuments, Split

Date: 29th April 2025

Site Description:

In front of the Museum of Croatian Archaeological Monuments stands a group of stećci relocated from various sites in inland Dalmatia during the late 20th century. Their removal from original graves is now considered inappropriate, as it erased centuries-old burial contexts. Among them is the stećak of Jerko Kustražić, a medieval Vlah from Crljivica near Cista Velika, crafted by master smith Jurina, whose works appear across Dalmatia and Herzegovina. Originally paired with the stećak of his wife Vladna, which remains in Crljivica, it is decorated with a well-preserved depiction of a kolo (circle dance). The scene features five haloed figures holding flowers, linked within a rope-like border, leading to a larger figure holding a cross, symbolising the belief that “without a cross, there is no path to heaven.”

Location and Environment:

The site’s outdoor grassy terrain required preliminary grass cutting. Weather conditions were sunny and stable, providing ideal data acquisition conditions. Surrounding trees and buildings imposed slight constraints on drone flight paths.

Methodologies:

- Aerial Photogrammetry (automated and manual)
- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- 360° Imagery Capture

Aerial photogrammetry was used for large-scale capture of the entire site layout. Ground-based scans provided detailed imagery of each Stećci. 360° captures support contextual understanding and VR-compatible experiences.

Process:

A 360° tour was completed first, prior to placing photogrammetry targets, to record the site unobstructed. Subsequently, photogrammetry markers were strategically placed around individual Stećci, maintaining a minimum of three markers per monument to facilitate accurate reconstruction. Automated drone flights mapped the site broadly, followed by manual flights focusing on occluded areas. Ground-based photogrammetry captured detailed images of individual tombstones and a general site overview. Separate SD cards were used to segment datasets for streamlined post-processing.

Total scanned monuments: 8

Difficulties/Constraints:

Uncut grass initially delayed setup. Tree and building proximity necessitated adjustments to drone flight plans to avoid obstructions.

Site 2: Crljivica Necropolis, Cista Velika

Date: 30th April 2025

Site Description:

The Crljivica site near Cista Provo, a UNESCO-listed complex, is the largest and most significant group of stećci in Croatia, with evidence of habitation from prehistoric times to the late Middle Ages. It comprises Mala gomila, Velika gomila, and a sinkhole with wells. The 14th–15th century cemetery contains around 90 stećci; slabs, chests, ridge-shaped tombstones, and 16 sarcophagi decorated with crosses, lilies, hunting and dance scenes, plant motifs, crescents, and stars.

Located along the ancient Tilurium–Narona road, Velika Crljivica is the largest cluster, while Mala Crljivica holds fewer, though decorated, tombstones. South of Velika Crljivica, a sinkhole contains seven medieval wells, likely of Roman origin, used until the 20th century. Road works and atmospheric exposure have damaged the site, with erosion and temperature fluctuations posing ongoing risks.

Location and Environment:

The terrain includes sloped areas with a road dividing the site into two parts. Weather was clear and sunny. Brief interruptions occurred due to visitor presence.

Methodologies:

- Aerial Photogrammetry (automated and manual)
- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- 360° Imagery Capture

As with the first site, aerial and ground-based photogrammetry ensured accurate spatial documentation and high-resolution models of each Stećci, while 360° captures added immersive context.

Process:

The session began with a systematic 360° tour to capture the environmental context and site layout before placing photogrammetry markers. Markers were then distributed, with three per Stećci where possible, paying special attention to safely crossing the dividing road. Automated and manual drone flights covered the entire site, with manual flights focused on areas near roads and tree lines. Ground-based photogrammetry was conducted in two phases: detailed individual Stećci capture and broader site sweeps. Data was managed via separate SD cards for clarity during post-processing.

Total scanned monuments: 10

Difficulties/Constraints:

The dividing road required careful logistics and safety measures during equipment transport. Tree coverage complicated drone flight paths. Visitor interruptions and sloped terrain presented minor workflow challenges.

Fig. 15: Museum of Croatian Archaeological Monuments; on-site work in progress

Fig. 16: Crljivica Necropolis

Fig. 17: Crljivica Necropolis; on site work in progress

1.5 KOPOŠIĆI NECROPOLIS, KRIŽEVIĆI NECROPOLIS AND THE NATIONAL MUSEUM (SARAJEVO) – BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA 2025

HM Acquisition Team: Francesco Vella (Photogrammetry Specialist and Lidar Operator), Kyle Attard (Photogrammetry Specialist), Aaron Edward Cole (Drone Pilot & Photogrammetry Specialist), Anthony Cassar (Low-Cost Digitisation Specialist)

On-site Partners: (UNSA) Nusret Dreskovic, Saida Ibragic, Edin Bujak, Edin Hrelja, Perica Mijatović, Zlatan Filipović

QAB Member: Marinos Ioannides

Dates of Acquisition: 26th – 30th May 2025

Site 1: Kopošići Necropolis

Date: 27th May 2025

Site Description:

Kopošići, near Ilijaš in central Bosnia, hosts a necropolis of late 14th–early 15th century stećci, including the monumental tomb of Bosnian prince Batić Mirković. His nine-ton stećak bears an inscription noting his service under King Tvrtko II Kotromanić and his burial by his wife, Vukava, on his estate. Local tradition associates adjacent monuments with Vukava and Batić's father, Prince Mirko Radojević. The site features eight prominent stećci at its center and about 30 more along the slope. Batić's stećak, over two meters long and decorated with intricate ribbon motifs, is regarded as one of the finest examples of the type. The necropolis is in poor condition, with cracks threatening the stones, highlighting the need for urgent conservation.

Location and Environment:

The site is situated on a slope surrounded by dense tree coverage, resulting in partial shading and restricted aerial manoeuvrability. Weather conditions were overcast in the morning, gradually clearing to intermittent sun, creating variable lighting conditions during acquisition.

Methodologies:

- Aerial Photogrammetry (automated and manual)
- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- 360° Imagery Capture

Drone photogrammetry was particularly important for capturing the full site model, while handheld photogrammetry was essential for focusing on individual stećci. The 360-degree tour was a required component of the project and will be used to make the site more accessible via virtual tours.

Process:

The scanning process began with an initial drone imaging session to mitigate the risk posed by the adverse weather. Once the aerial coverage was complete, half the team moved on to do the acquisition of the individual stećci, whilst the other half of the team focused on gathering examples

of low-cost digitisation data and gaussian splat data. This was followed by a full-site ground-based photogrammetry session, after which a second drone pass was conducted to fill any gaps in coverage. The session concluded with the production of a 360-degree virtual tour.

Total scanned monuments: 8

Difficulties/Constraints:

The acquisition process faced several challenges, including limited drone access in certain areas due to the close proximity of surrounding trees. Additionally, fluctuating sunlight caused by intermittent cloud cover created inconsistent lighting, which complicated the photogrammetry process and required frequent adjustments to camera settings to maintain image quality and consistency.

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Site 2: Križeviči Necropolis

Date: 28th May 2025 | 09:00 – 15:30

Site Description:

The Gradina necropolis in Križeviči near Olovo, at the confluence of the Očevlje and Orlje streams, contains 42 limestone stećci; six slabs, six chests, 29 gabled-roof types with plinths, and one rare double gabled-roof stećak carved from a single monolith. Ten monuments feature spirals, rosettes, twisted ribbons, stars, and scenes such as a horseman and a hand holding a spear. The most ornate stećak, nearly 2.5 m long, is richly decorated on all sides with rosettes, spirals, grape clusters, and zigzags, and appears on the 10 convertibles Bosnian marka banknote. The site likely overlays a prehistoric settlement and is considered one of Bosnia's most significant for its craftsmanship and ornamentation.

Location and Environment:

The site is located on a slope and is almost completely covered by trees and dense foliage. Weather conditions were generally sunny, though occasional cloud cover caused slight lighting inconsistencies. Due to the heavy tree coverage, traditional drone photogrammetry was not feasible, leading the team to rely on LiDAR scanning as the primary method of acquisition.

Methodologies:

- Terrestrial LiDAR Scanning
- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- 360° Imagery Capture
- Low-Cost Digitisation with Gaussian splatting using an *Avata* drone

These methods were chosen to address specific site constraints: LiDAR was essential due to the inability to perform large-scale aerial photogrammetry under the dense canopy; photogrammetry complemented the LiDAR data by capturing detailed textures of the site and *stećci*; and the *Avata* drone was selected for its ability to navigate tight spaces and record comprehensive visual coverage.

Process:

Given the site's size and challenging conditions, each team member was assigned a distinct role. One operator conducted LiDAR scanning, beginning with the highest settings for maximum detail but later switching to medium settings to ensure the scan was completed within the available time. A second member performed photogrammetry of the entire site to enhance the LiDAR dataset. A third team member concentrated on photogrammetry of eight individual stećci or groups of stećci. Then, a 360 tour of the site was captured. Finally, the drone specialist piloted the Avata drone through confined spaces to capture video footage for Gaussian splatting.

Total scanned monuments: 8

Difficulties/Constraints:

The most significant challenge was the dense tree coverage, which made traditional aerial photogrammetry impossible and necessitated the use of LiDAR. This method, while effective, produced large datasets and required considerable time to operate. Additionally, intermittent cloud cover caused inconsistent lighting, causing the photogrammetry specialists to adjust their camera settings mid-scan to maintain optimal exposure.

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Site 3: National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina

Date: 29th May 2025 | 08:45 – 14:30

Site Description:

The artificial necropolis of stećci at the National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina in Sarajevo houses 37 monuments relocated over the past century from various sites to protect them from damage. Most are richly decorated, many bearing epitaphs, and collectively represent the full range of stećci shapes, ornamentation, and geographical distribution. Key examples include the renowned stećak from Zgošća near Kakanj, a masterpiece of medieval sepulchral art, and some of the largest monuments, such as those from Lađevina near Rogatica, weighing around 20 tons. The stećci are displayed in the botanical garden, the museum's front garden, the medieval exhibition, and near the ethnology department. However, relocation has exposed them to a new climatic environment and urban pollutants, which negatively affect their preservation. These stone tombstones, sourced from various sites across the country, feature decorative carvings and inscriptions.

Location and Environment:

The site is flat, with neatly cut grass directly in front of the museum building. Weather conditions were overcast, providing diffused lighting. The location is near the U.S. Embassy, which imposed restrictions on the maximum altitude the drone could fly, directly influencing the scanning approach.

Methodologies:

- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- Aerial Photogrammetry

Manual drone scanning was necessary because altitude restrictions prevented the use of automated flight paths. Ground-based photogrammetry was chosen to capture detailed textures and geometry of each monument, while the drone was also used for high or large stećci where camera access was limited due to the scale of the monuments (height).

Process:

The session began with the drone pilot conducting a manual photogrammetry scan of the entire site, capturing five sets of images: one top-down set and four angled sets taken at 45 degrees from each side toward the stećci. Following this, two team members carried out ground-based photogrammetry of all ten stećci, while the drone pilot supplemented these efforts with aerial passes for the tallest monuments to ensure complete coverage. Finally, a 360 tour of the site was captured.

Total scanned monuments: 10

Difficulties/Constraints:

The primary constraints included the size and height of certain stećci, which required multiple passes with both drone and camera to achieve complete coverage. Additionally, the proximity to the U.S. Embassy prevented the use of automated drone scanning and limited flight altitude, making the process more time-intensive and reliant on manual piloting.

Attendance of the QAB

The Quality Advisory Board (QAB) in the STECCI project ensures that digitisation workflows, acquisition strategies, and resulting outputs meet the highest recognised standards in cultural heritage documentation. During the Bosnia and Herzegovina fieldwork, the team was joined on-site by Professor Marinos Ioannides, UNESCO Chair on Digital Cultural Heritage and STECCI QAB member. His presence was instrumental in reviewing and validating the applied methodologies, confirming their alignment with the quality benchmarks established by the *VIGIE Study on Quality in 3D Digitisation of Tangible Cultural Heritage* and broader European policies. This engagement not only reinforced methodological rigour but also provided targeted expert feedback, supporting the continuous refinement of acquisition protocols in line with both project-specific and sector-wide standards.

Fig. 18: On- Site team

Fig. 19: Kopošići (Site 1); work in progress

Fig. 20: Kriševići (Site 2); work in progress

Fig. 21: National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Site 3)

1.6 CIMETIÈRE SAINT JEAN (CAEN), FRANCE 2025

HM Acquisition Team: Kyle Attard (Photogrammetry Specialist), Jacob Saliba (Photogrammetry Specialist), Warren Attard (LiDAR Operator)

On-site Partners: (IMT) Vincent Thiery

Dates of Acquisition: 18th – 19th June 2025

Site: Cimetière Saint Jean, Caen

Date: 18th June 2025

Site Description:

The Saint-Jean cemetery in Caen, Normandy, France, is an abandoned graveyard established in the 1780s, originally situated outside the city limits. It occupies the heart of an ancient quarry of the renowned “stone of Caen,” a limestone quarried since Roman times and widely used in monumental architecture, including Canterbury Cathedral. With urban expansion, the cemetery is now surrounded by buildings and has been abandoned for decades. Shaded by trees and located in a quiet area, the site conveys a sense of stillness. It has been protected since 1939. The cemetery was chosen for study due to its proximity to the sea, accessibility, and the local availability of Caen limestone as a reference material. The climate is classified as Cfb (temperate oceanic).

Location and Environment:

The acquisition was carried out in an abandoned cemetery characterised by medium-sized trees, dense foliage, and uneven ground covered with grass. The site’s conditions, including limited accessibility and visual obstructions, led us to opt for LiDAR and terrestrial photogrammetry. While the weather was generally sunny and favourable for scanning, the strong sunlight created harsh highlights in some areas, affecting scan quality. At the same time, the tree cover produced varying levels of shade, particularly around limestone monuments, and the overgrown grass partially obscured details on the stones, making accurate documentation more challenging.

Methodologies:

- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR)

Photogrammetry was employed to capture the monument details, while LiDAR provided high-precision measurements of the monuments’ dimensions.

Process:

Both photogrammetry and LiDAR were used to document the site, working as a three-person team: one member operated the LiDAR scanner, while the other two handled photogrammetry using two cameras, one of which equipped with a flash rig to manage shaded areas under the trees. The team began by strategically placing targets around selected monuments to aid in aligning the scans. In collaboration with local partners (IMT), the tombstones that needed higher quality acquisition were identified. While the photogrammetry specialists focused on photographing these

priority monuments, the LiDAR operator simultaneously scanned other areas of the site. For taller structures, a ladder was used to capture the upper sections accurately.

Total scanned monuments: 8

Difficulties/Constraints:

Dense foliage restricted 360-degree visibility of certain monuments, while unstable ground conditions around some structures limited movement and access for full coverage. These factors prevented complete capture of a few monuments' upper sections.

Fig. 22: Cimetière Saint Jean, Caen

Fig. 23: On-site work in progress

1.7 MRAMORJE (PERUĆAC), SERBIA 2025

HM Acquisition Team: Kyle Attard (Photogrammetry Specialist), Warren Attard (Photogrammetry Specialist), Myron Saliba (LiDAR Operator)

On-site Partners: (UNSPMF) Boško Petrov

Dates of Acquisition: 16th – 17th July 2025

Site: Mramorje - Perućac, Serbia,

Date: 16th July 2025

Site Description:

Mramorje, also known as Bagruša, is a 14th-century medieval necropolis of stećak tombstones located at the entrance to the settlement of Perućac, Serbia, between the Drina River and the main road that follows its course. Recognized for its historical and cultural significance, it was inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List in 2016 and represents the largest concentration of stećci in Serbia. Originally comprising around 200 tombstones, 93 remain today, including slab tombstones, gabled forms with and without bases, chest-shaped monuments, and a few amorphous stones, predominantly arranged in regular west-east rows according to medieval burial customs. Many tombstones feature simple decorative motifs such as circles, crescent moons, swords, and shields, while others are plain, and a small number have been relocated to museum collections in Belgrade and Užice. The necropolis sits at an altitude of approximately 280 meters above sea level within the Drina River valley, surrounded by karstic terrain and influenced by a humid continental climate. Despite its protected status, Mramorje faces threats from natural erosion caused by the nearby river and pressures from urban expansion, making conservation efforts essential to preserve this remarkable example of medieval sepulchral art.

Location and Environment:

The site is in an open area with grass and uneven ground. The weather was mostly cloudy, with a bit of sun from time to time.

Methodologies:

- Ground-Based Photogrammetry
- Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR)
- Low-cost methodology (Poly Cam, Reality Capture)

Photogrammetry was employed to capture the site's layout and Stećci details, while LiDAR provided an alternative to aerial photogrammetry to get a full scan of the whole site.

Process:

Fieldwork was carried out in Mramorje, Perućac, Serbia, to document the stećci monuments using a combination of professional and low-cost 3D scanning methods. The techniques applied were photogrammetry and LiDAR scanning. The process began with the scanning of individual monuments. Two photogrammetry setups were used, one equipped with a flash rig and one

without. To enhance accuracy and facilitate alignment, targets were placed around each monument during this stage. After completing the individual scans, the entire site was scanned using a professional LiDAR scanner. Following the LiDAR scan, the site was also scanned by photogrammetry using a camera without a flash rig. To assess low-cost alternatives, mobile phones running Polycam (for both LiDAR and photogrammetry) and RealityScan were used.

Total scanned monuments: 7

Difficulties/Constraints:

While this site would have been well suited for the integration of aerial photogrammetry alongside other methodologies, strict regulations from the national aviation authorities prohibited drone operations without completing a locally administered licensing test. Given the project's timeframe, this was not feasible.

Fig. 24: Mramorje; on-site work in progress; LiDAR set-up

Fig. 25: Mramorje; on-site work in progress; Photogrammetry set-up

1.8 DOMVS ROMANA (RABAT), MALTA 2025

HM Acquisition Team: Warren Attard (Photogrammetry Specialist), Myron Saliba (Photogrammetry Specialist), Aaron Edward Cole (Drone Operator), Julian Barbara (Videographer)

Dates of Acquisition: 22nd – 23rd July 2025

Site: Domvs Romana – Rabat, Malta

Date: 22nd July 2025 (scan 1)

Site Description:

Located in Rabat, Malta, the Domvs Roman was originally constructed before the beginning of the 1st century BC, the Domus Romana functioned as an aristocratic townhouse, adorned with fine polychrome mosaics, comparable to those found in Pompeii and Sicily, as well as a colonnaded peristyle. The site's architectural and artistic features, including mosaic pavements, painted wall plaster, and statuary, reflect the influence of Hellenistic and Roman artistic traditions. Water irrigation and cistern systems also point to elaborate engineering. The site's historical significance extends beyond the Roman period; by the 11th century, under the Fatimid Caliphate and into the early Norman period, the area was repurposed as a Muslim cemetery, with over 245 burials. The multi-period use of the site highlights the evolving cultural landscape of Malta over centuries.

Location and Environment:

The selected scanning site has an open-air archaeological location with exposed structures. On this date, the weather was sunny and with standard July temperatures in the mid-to-high 30 degrees Celsius hot, creating harsh lighting conditions and strong contrasting shadows. Light rigs were used to soften shadows on the individual objects.

Methodologies:

- Hand-Held Photogrammetry
- Aerial Photogrammetry

Aerial photogrammetry was used to document the entire site layout, while hand-held photogrammetry captured high-resolution detail of both the site structures and the four priority artefacts.

Process:

Both aerial and hand-held photogrammetry techniques were employed for the four individual objects of the site as well as site-wide.

Total scanned monuments: 4

Difficulties/Constraints:

A technical issue occurred with the drone, resulting in the loss of some aerial data. The absence of photogrammetry targets, a deliberate decision for this project, later enabled a clean retake

without mismatched data. Further to the technical issue, harsh sunlight caused issues requiring the team to use artificial lighting to control the direction of shadows for the object scans. The temperature and heat on this day also caused the photogrammetry rigs to overheat.

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Date: 31st July 2025 | 08:30 – 10:00 (Scan 2)

Overview of 3D Scanned Assets:

This session focused solely on retaking the aerial photogrammetry dataset lost during the 22nd July session.

Location/Environment Details:

The weather conditions, the lack of wind and the light conditions of the early morning were perfect for aerial acquisition.

Methodologies:

- Aerial Photogrammetry (Automated and Manual)

To recapture the complete site layout from above, ensuring consistency with the previous ground-based and object-level photogrammetry.

Process

Aaron Edward Cole conducted a full aerial rescan of the site. The absence of targets ensured the dataset could be merged without mismatches.

Difficulties/Constraints:

None.

Fig. 26: Domvs Romana; Full site view

Fig. 27: Domvs Romana; on-site work in progress

Fig. 28: Domvs Romana; on-site work in progress

1.9 UNSLEBEN, KLEINBARDORF, GERMANY 2025

HM Acquisition Team: Jacob (Photogrammetry Specialist), Warren Attard (Photogrammetry Specialist), Aaron Edward Cole (Drone Operator)

On-site Partners: (SPK) Stefan Simon, Abdelrhman Fahmy

Dates of Acquisition: 4th – 8th August 2025

Site: Kleinbardorf

Date: 5th August 2025

Site Description:

Kleinbardorf, a village in Ebern, Lower Franconia, Bavaria, is home to the Judenhügel, a medieval Jewish cemetery established in the 16th century and one of the largest in Bavaria, containing around 4,400 gravestones that served 27 surrounding communities until the 20th century. The cemetery, enclosed by an early medieval circular wall, features mostly sandstone gravestones with some limestone, ranging from 1 to 1.5 meters tall, with larger stones for prominent individuals displaying intricate motifs reflecting social status. Situated about 10 km northeast of Ebern in a humid continental climate, the site traces human settlement in the region back to 10,000 BC and illustrates the village's historical role as a key route linking southern and northern Germany by the 8th century. Selected as a case study, Kleinbardorf offers rich insights into Jewish burial traditions and epigraphic heritage.

Location and Environment:

The cemetery is an open landscape with dense monument placement and significant tree coverage. The tree canopy posed challenges for drone operation, while the tightly packed gravestones required careful manoeuvring for terrestrial photogrammetry. Weather was overcast, which helped manage shadows, but frequent light showers interrupted aerial work and slowed progress.

Methodologies:

- Terrestrial Photogrammetry
- Aerial Photogrammetry (Automated and Manual)
- Low-cost methodologies (Poly Cam, RealityScan)

Hand-held and aerial photogrammetry was used for detailed recording of the cemetery layout and individual monuments. The team captured a variety of techniques in low-cost alternatives to compare methodologies in deliverable 4.2.

Process:

The team began by placing photogrammetry targets around selected tombstones identified by local partners for high-detail scanning in the previsit acquisition report. Targets were positioned to enhance accuracy for these priority monuments. Aerial acquisition began with an automated drone scan of the entire site, followed by manual flights to cover difficult areas blocked by trees or tight

spacing. The drone operator worked gradually from higher altitudes to lower passes for optimal coverage. While the drone work progressed, the photogrammetry specialists documented the four selected individual tombstones, then moved to complete full-site terrestrial coverage. This was conducted row-by-row, capturing each monument from four angles to ensure complete visual data. Total scanned monuments: 5

Difficulties/Constraints:

The acquisition at Kleinbardorf was challenging due to the dense arrangement of monuments and narrow pathways, which complicated both aerial and ground-based coverage. Tree canopy interference affected drone flights, while frequent light showers caused multiple interruptions, slowing down the aerial photogrammetry process. The site's overall density resulted in a particularly large dataset, which is expected to increase the time and complexity of post-processing.

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Site: Unsleben

Date: 6th August 2025

Site Description:

The Jewish cemetery in Unsleben, Lower Franconia, Bavaria, established in the 17th century, served the burial needs of the local Jewish community until the Holocaust and today stands as a listed monument under German heritage preservation laws. Situated on the outskirts of Unsleben amidst a peaceful rural landscape with views toward the village, the cemetery experiences a humid continental climate, contributing to natural weathering patterns on the stones. Unsleben provides valuable insights into Jewish funerary traditions, long-term preservation of cultural landscapes, and the spatial organisation of rural cemeteries.

Location and Environment:

The site is situated on a steep hill with open views, with tree coverage limited to the site's edges. The slope created operational challenges for both drone and ground-based acquisition, particularly for maintaining stable flight paths. Due to elevation changes, drone operations were performed entirely in manual mode. Weather was generally good, though harsh shadows were present during full-site photogrammetry.

Methodologies:

- Terrestrial Photogrammetry
- Aerial Photogrammetry
- Low-cost methodologies (Poly Cam, RealityScan)

Hand-held and aerial photogrammetry was used for detailed recording of the cemetery layout and individual monuments. The team captured a variety of techniques in low-cost alternatives to compare methodologies in deliverable 4.2.

Process:

The team began by strategically placing photogrammetry targets around the identified tomb stones by the local partners, they identified which tombstones required more detailed scanning, positioning the targets closer to those tombstones for higher accuracy.

Once the targets were set, the drone pilot initiated a manual photogrammetry scan of the entire site. After this he did two hyperlapses to cover the rest of the area. Following these steps, the drone operator also took some individual photos of the top areas of the individual monuments as to aid the other photogrammetry specialists.

During the manual drone photogrammetry of the site the two other photogrammetry specialists completed the individual monuments using high quality photogrammetry followed by the low-cost methodologies completing a poly scan (photogrammetry) with an iPhone and a Samsung mobile followed by a LIDAR scan using Polycam with an iPhone and 2 identical scans using a both the iPhone and the Samsung with reality scan.

Following this the photogrammetry specialists concluded the scanning session by taking terrestrial photogrammetry of the full site. These were conducted by taking photos of the full site capturing the tombs from four different angles row by row until the full area was covered.

Total scanned monuments: 4

Difficulties/Constraints:

The steep slope of the site made both aerial and ground coverage physically and technically demanding, with drone flights requiring full manual control to accommodate the elevation differences. Harsh lighting created high-contrast shadows that complicated the full-site photogrammetry, while dense vegetation in certain sections restricted access to some gravestones. In addition, the far ends of the cemetery were bordered by large trees, which may affect the final visual quality of certain monuments.

Fig. 29: Kleinbardorf; on-site work in progress

Fig. 30: Unsleben; on-site work in progress

OUTLOOK

Milestone 5 has been successfully achieved, with all physical fieldwork for the 3D acquisition of sites and selected monuments completed using a combination of LiDAR, aerial and terrestrial photogrammetry, and supplementary techniques. Throughout all on-site scans, data from both photogrammetry and LiDAR workflows were duplicated onto two SSDs to ensure redundancy. Initial processing and pre-testing visualisation of point clouds were conducted *in situ* to verify data quality and completeness before leaving each site, allowing for timely adjustments where necessary. Following this milestone, efforts will continue with post-processing and production of the final digital assets, culminating in Milestone 6 at Month 36, when these assets will be disseminated via the STECCI platform and publicly published with the appropriate permissions, following review and approval by the relevant stakeholders. Additionally, this acquisition phase also contributes to Deliverable 4.2, specifically in testing and refining low-cost digitisation methodologies and the “What to Scan” protocol under real field conditions.

APPENDIX

Para data documentation

The appendices in this report contain paradata reports for each site acquisition. This includes information on scanning conditions, equipment settings, environmental factors, workflow adjustments, and any challenges encountered during the data capture. Recording paradata ensures the acquisition was conducted optimally and thoroughly records every step of the process. This also enhances transparency, explains the final Model quality while supporting future use.

APPENDIX 1.1 HUNDSKIRCHE, AUSTRIA

Equipment Used

Photogrammetry Equipment

- 2x Sony alpha 6100 equipped with G-Master II 24-70 telephoto lens
- 2x variable polarizer
- 2x Godox AR 400 flash

LiDAR Equipment

- 1x Leica RTC360 3D Laser Scanner

RTI Equipment

- 1x Nikon Z 7II equipped with Nikkor Z 24-70 telephoto lens
- 1x Broncolor scope D50 RTI
- Other
- 1x Colourchecker
- 20x AprilTags / Targets
- 1x Sony alpha6000 (for Documentation)

Acquisition Para data

Graffiti 1

- Photogrammetry – Scan1 (with flash)
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 964
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/20
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Photogrammetry – Scan2
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 755
 - Shutter Speed: 1/100
 - ISO: 3200
 - Aperture: f/7.1
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- LiDAR – Scan1

- LiDAR Setups: 8
- LiDAR – Scan2
 - LiDAR Setups: 7
- RT1 – Set1
 - Image Format: NEF
 - Number of Images taken: 96 (1 set with colourchecker, 1 without colourchecker)
 - Shutter Speed: 1/30
 - ISO: 400
 - Aperture: f/11
 - Dimensions: 8288x5520
 - Focal Length: 28mm
- RT1 – Set2
 - Image Format: NEF
 - Number of Images taken: 96 (1 set with colourchecker, 1 without colourchecker)
 - Shutter Speed: 1/30
 - ISO: 400
 - Aperture: f/11
 - Dimensions: 8288x5520
 - Focal Length: 28mm
- RT1 – Set3
 - Image Format: NEF
 - Number of Images taken: 96 (1 set with colourchecker, 1 without colourchecker)
 - Shutter Speed: 1/30
 - ISO: 400
 - Aperture: f/11
 - Dimensions: 8288x5520
 - Focal Length: 28mm

Graffiti 2

- Photogrammetry – Scan1 (with flash)
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 406
 - Shutter Speed: 1/100
 - ISO: 3200
 - Aperture: f/7.1
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24-70mm (varied because data was captured from a distance of 5m)
- LiDAR – Scan1
 - LiDAR Setups: 5

APPENDIX 1.2 ŽUGIĆA BARE, MONTENEGRO

Equipment Used for Both Areas

Photogrammetry Equipment

- 2x Sony alpha 6100 equipped with G-Master II 24-70 telephoto lens
- 2x variable polarizer
- 2x Godox AR 400 flash
- 1x Autel Evo 3 v1 Drone

LiDAR Equipment

- 1x Leica RTC360 3D Laser Scanner
- 1x Tablet for data processing

Other

- 1x Colourchecker
- 20x AprilTags / Targets
- 1x Sony alpha6000 (for Documentation)

Acquisition Para data – Area 1

Scan 1

- Automated Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 1834
 - Shutter Speed: 1/40
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 7680x4320
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm
- Manual Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 164
 - Shutter Speed: 1/80
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 8000x6000
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm
- Ground Based Photogrammetry of Site
 - Image Format: JPG

- Number of Images taken: 380
- Shutter Speed: 1/125
- ISO: 100
- Aperture: f/10
- Dimensions: 6000x4000
- Focal Length: 24mm

- LiDAR
 - LiDAR Setups: 62

- Individual Stecci 1 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 107
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 2 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 96
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 3 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 139
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 4 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 153
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 5 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW

- Number of Images taken: 155
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 6 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 169
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 7 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 203
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

Scan 2

- Manual Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 382
 - Shutter Speed: 1/640
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 8000x6000
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm
- Ground Based Photogrammetry of Site
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 970
 - Shutter Speed: 1/500
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/9
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 35mm

- LiDAR
 - LiDAR Setups: 59

- Individual Stecci 1 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 213
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 2 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 160
 - Shutter Speed: 1/160
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 3 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 148
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 4 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 113
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 5 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 192
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 6 High Resolution Photogrammetry

- Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 130
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 7 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 265
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 8 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 312
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 9 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG,ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 335
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

Acquisition Para data – Area 2

- Automated Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, DNG
 - Number of Images taken: 553
 - Shutter Speed: 1/640
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 7680x4320
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm
- Manual Aerial Photogrammetry

- Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 249
 - Shutter Speed: 1/640
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 8000x6000
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm
- Ground Based Photogrammetry of Site
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 542
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125 – 1/640
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 16mm/19mm
- LiDAR
 - LiDAR Setups: 35
- Individual Stecci 1 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 293
 - Shutter Speed: 1/160
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 2 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 203
 - Shutter Speed: 1/160
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 3 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 173
 - Shutter Speed: 1/160
 - ISO: 100

- Aperture: f/10
- Dimensions: 6000x4000
- Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 4 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 79
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/13
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 5 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 99
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/8
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 6 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 312
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/8
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 7 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 155
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 8 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 131

- Shutter Speed: 1/200
- ISO: 100
- Aperture: f/10
- Dimensions: 6000x4000
- Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 9 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 383
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

APPENDIX 1.3 RAVANJSKA VRATA (KUPRES), RADIMLJA (STOLAC), BLIDINJE (DUGO POLJE) – BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

Equipment Used for All Sites

Photogrammetry Equipment

- 2x Sony alpha 6100 equipped with G-Master II 24-70 telephoto lens
- 2x variable polarizer
- 2x Godox AR 400 flash
- 1x Autel Evo 3 v1 Drone

LiDAR Equipment

- 1x Leica RTC360 3D Laser Scanner
- 1x Tablet for data processing

Other

- 1x Colourchecker
- 30x AprilTags / Targets
- 1x Sony alpha6000 (for Documentation)

Blidinje Paradata Acquisition

- Automated Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 537
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 400
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 7680x4320
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm
- Manual Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 606
 - Shutter Speed: 1/240
 - ISO: 200
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 8000x6000
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm

- Ground Based Photogrammetry of Site
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 1000
 - Shutter Speed: 1/160
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- LiDAR
 - LiDAR Setups: 59

- Individual Stecci 1 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 376
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 2 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 651
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 3 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 271
 - Shutter Speed: 1/80
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 4 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 391

- Shutter Speed: 1/160
- ISO: 100
- Aperture: f/10
- Dimensions: 6000x4000
- Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 5 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 189
 - Shutter Speed: 1/160
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 6 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 356
 - Shutter Speed: 1/160
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 7 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 851
 - Shutter Speed: 1/160
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 8 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 281
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

Ravanjska Vrata Paradata Acquisition

- Automated Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 391
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 400
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 7680x4320
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm

- Manual Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 558
 - Shutter Speed: 1/320
 - ISO: 200
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 8000x6000
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm

- Ground Based Photogrammetry of Site
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 833
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- LiDAR
 - LiDAR Setups: 44

- Individual Stecci 1 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 781
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 2 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW

- Number of Images taken: 844
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 3 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 237
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/5
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 4 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 372
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 5 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 279
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 6 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 409
 - Shutter Speed: 1/250
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/5
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

Radimlja Paradata Acquisition

- Automated Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 689
 - Shutter Speed: 1/200
 - ISO: 800
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 7680x4320
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm

- Manual Aerial Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG
 - Number of Images taken: 1057
 - Shutter Speed: 1/240
 - ISO: 200
 - Aperture: f/1.8
 - Dimensions: 8000x6000
 - Focal Length: 35 mm format equivalent focal length: 29 mm

- Ground Based Photogrammetry of Site
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 1531
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- LiDAR
 - LiDAR Scan1 Setups: 48
 - LiDAR Scan2 Setups: 8

- Individual Stecci 1 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 1015
 - Shutter Speed: 1/100
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 2 High Resolution Photogrammetry

- Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 623
 - Shutter Speed: 1/100
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 3 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 498
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 4 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 1077
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 5 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 813
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 100
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm
- Individual Stecci 6 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 766
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 160
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

- Individual Stecci 7 High Resolution Photogrammetry
 - Image Format: JPG, ARW
 - Number of Images taken: 1211
 - Shutter Speed: 1/125
 - ISO: 160
 - Aperture: f/10
 - Dimensions: 6000x4000
 - Focal Length: 24mm

APPENDIX 1.4 CRLJIVICA NECROPOLIS (CISTA VELIKA), MUSEUM OF CROATIAN ARCHAEOLOGICAL MONUMENTS (SPLIT) – CROATIA

Equipment Used on all sites

DRONE EQUIPMENT

- DRONE Autel Evo-II Pro

PHOTOGRAMMETRY EQUIPMENT

Setup 1

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash Ringflash (Godox Wistro AR400)
- Filter None

Setup 2

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash None
- Filter None

Setup 3

- Camera Sony A6000
- Lens Sony 16-50mm lens SEL16F28
- Flash None
- Filter None

Museum of Croatian Archaeological Monuments Paradata Acquisition

PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Museum Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 102
 - Shutter Speed 1/160
 - ISO 200 - 400
 - Aperture f/1.8
 - Resolution 7680x4320
 - Focal Length 5mm

MANUAL AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Museum Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 2

- Image Format JPEG/RAW
- Number of Images 584
- Shutter Speed 1/120
- ISO 200 - 400
- Aperture f/1.8
- Resolution 960x540
- Focal Length 5mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Stecci in Museum Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 3
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1504
 - Shutter Speed 1/200
 - ISO 100
 - Aperture f/8
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Stecci in Museum Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 4
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1152
 - Shutter Speed 1/200
 - ISO 100
 - Aperture f/8
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Museum Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 5
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 2
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 423
 - Shutter Speed 1/320
 - ISO 100
 - Aperture f/11
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Museum Site
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 3
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 255
 - Shutter Speed 1/200
 - ISO 160
 - Aperture f/14
 - Resolution 6024x4024
 - Focal Length 17mm

Crljivica Necropolis Paradata Acquisition

AUTOMATED AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Crljivica Necropolis Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 2227
 - Shutter Speed 1/240
 - ISO 200 - 400
 - Aperture f/1.8
 - Resolution 7680x4320
 - Focal Length 5mm

MANUAL AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Crljivica Necropolis Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 2
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 922
 - Shutter Speed Jan-60
 - ISO 200 - 400
 - Aperture f/1.8
 - Resolution 7680x4320
 - Focal Length 5mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Stecci in Crljivica Necropolis Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 3
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1666
 - Shutter Speed 1/200

- ISO 100
- Aperture f/11
- Resolution 6000x4000
- Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Stecci in Crljivica Necropolis Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 4
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1889
 - Shutter Speed 1/200
 - ISO 100
 - Aperture f/8
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Crljivica Necropolis Site
 - Name/Number of Scan 5
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 2
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1310
 - Shutter Speed 1/160
 - ISO 160
 - Aperture f/13
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Crljivica Necropolis Site
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 2
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 719
 - Shutter Speed 1/160
 - ISO 160
 - Aperture f/13
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Crljivica Necropolis Site
 - Name/Number of Scan

- Camera Setup Used Setup 3
- Image Format JPEG/RAW
- Number of Images 862
- Shutter Speed 1/1250
- ISO 100
- Aperture f/3.5
- Resolution 6000x4000
- Focal Length 16mm

APPENDIX 1.5 KOPOŠIĆI NECROPOLIS, KRIŽEVIĆI NECROPOLIS AND THE NATIONAL MUSEUM (SARAJEVO) – BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

Kopošići necropolis Paradata Acquisition

Equipment used

DRONE EQUIPMENT

- DRONE Autel Evo-II Pro

PHOTOGRAMMETRY EQUIPMENT

Setup 1

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash None
- Filter None

Setup 2

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash None
- Filter None
- Setup 3

AUTOMATED AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Drone Automated
 - Name/Number of Scan 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 105
 - Shutter Speed 1/400 - 1/160
 - ISO 100- 800
 - Aperture f1.8
 - Resolution 7680x4320
 - Focal Length 4.74

MANUAL AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Drone Manual
 - Name/Number of Scan 2
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 251
 - Shutter Speed 1/400 - 1/200
 - ISO 100-400
 - Aperture f1.8
 - Resolution 7640x4320
 - Focal Length 4.74

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Kyle- Individual Stecci in Koposici
 - Name/Number of Scan 3
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1,491
 - Shutter Speed 1/160
 - ISO 100-320
 - Aperture f8.0
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Francesco- Individual Stecci in Koposici
 - Name/Number of Scan 4
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1,372
 - Shutter Speed 1/160
 - ISO 100-160
 - Aperture f8.0 - 10.0
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site Koposici
 - Name/Number of Scan 5
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1,290
 - Shutter Speed 1/160
 - ISO 100-160
 - Aperture f8.0-11.0
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

Križeviči necropolis Paradata Acquisition

Equipment used

PHOTOGRAMMETRY EQUIPMENT

Setup 1

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash None
- Filter None

Setup 2

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash None
- Filter None

LiDAR EQUIPMENT

- LiDAR Leica RTC 360
- Total Station None
- DRONE EQUIPMENT
- DRONE Autel Evo-II Pro

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Krisevici
 - Name/Number of Scan 1
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 3,521
 - Shutter Speed 1/160
 - ISO 100-800
 - Aperture f8.0-11.0
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

LiDAR PARADATA

- Name of Object Krisevici
 - Name/Number of Scan 2
 - Number of Points 72
 - What level of detail Med/High

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site Krisevici

- Name/Number of Scan 2
- Camera Setup Used Setup 1
- Image Format JPEG/RAW
- Number of Images 3,895
- Shutter Speed 1/200 - 1/160
- ISO 125-3200
- Aperture 4.5-13.0
- Resolution 6000x4000
- Focal Length 24mm

AUTOMATED AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Site Krisevici
 - Name/Number of Scan 3
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 115
 - Shutter Speed 1/240-1/200
 - ISO 100-200
 - Aperture 1.8
 - Resolution 7680-4320
 - Focal Length 4.74

[The National Museum of Bosnia and Herzegovina Paradata Acquisition](#)

Equipment used

DRONE EQUIPMENT

- DRONE Autel Evo-II Pro

PHOTOGRAMMETRY EQUIPMENT

Setup 1

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash None
- Filter None

Setup 2

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash None
- Filter None

MANUAL AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site Drone

- Name/Number of Scan 1
- Image Format JPEG/RAW
- Number of Images 472
- Shutter Speed 1/200 -1/160
- ISO 100-200
- Aperture f1.8
- Resolution 7680x4320
- Focal Length 4.74

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual National Museum - Kyle
 - Name/Number of Scan 1
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 2,054
 - Shutter Speed 1/200 - 1/160
 - ISO 100 - 500
 - Aperture 1.8 - 13.0
 - Resolution 6000x4000

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual National Museum
 - Name/Number of Scan 2
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 2,054
 - Shutter Speed 1/200 - 1/160
 - ISO 100 - 400
 - Aperture 1.8 - 11.0
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object
 - Name/Number of Scan 3
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 533
 - Shutter Speed 1/160
 - ISO 100 - 320
 - Aperture 8.0 - 11.0
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

Equipment used

PHOTOGRAMMETRY EQUIPMENT

Setup 1

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash Ringflash (Godox Wistro AR400)
- Filter None

Setup 2

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash None
- Filter None

LiDAR EQUIPMENT

- LiDAR Leica RTC 360
- Total Station None

Cimetière Saint Jean Paradata Acquisition

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Limestone Monuments with Rig
 - Name/Number of Scan 1
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 2,026
 - Shutter Speed 1/160
 - ISO 100-500
 - Aperture f8.0
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Limestone Monuments
 - Name/Number of Scan 2
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 2
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1,682
 - Shutter Speed 1/80 - 1/100
 - ISO 800

- Aperture f6.3 / f7.1
- Resolution 6000x4000
- Focal Length 24

LiDAR PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Limestone Monuments
 - Name/Number of Scan 2
 - Number of Points 31
 - What level of detail High

APPENDIX 1.7 MRAMORJE, SERBIA

Equipment used

LiDAR EQUIPMENT

- LiDAR Leica RTC 360
- Total Station None

PHOTOGRAMMETRY EQUIPMENT

Setup 1

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash Ringflash (Godox Wistro AR400)
- Filter None

Setup 2

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash None
- Filter None

Mramorje Paradata Acquisition

LiDAR PARADATA

- Name of Object Full site
 - Name/Number of Scan 1
 - Number of Points 42
 - What level of detail Med/High

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual - Warren
 - Name/Number of Scan 2
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1,972
 - Shutter Speed 1/200
 - ISO 100
 - Aperture f7.1
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual - Kyle

- Name/Number of Scan 3
- Camera Setup Used Setup 2
- Image Format JPEG/RAW
- Number of Images 819
- Shutter Speed 1/160
- ISO 200-250
- Aperture f9.0
- Resolution 6000x4000
- Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full site - Warren
 - Name/Number of Scan 4
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 2
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 2986
 - Shutter Speed 1/640 - 1/250
 - ISO 200
 - Aperture f7.1
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

Equipment used

PHOTOGRAMMETRY EQUIPMENT

Setup 1

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash
- Filter

Setup 2

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash Ringflash (Godox Wistro AR400)
- Filter

DRONE EQUIPMENT

- DRONE Autel Evo II Dual 640T V3

Domvs Romana Paradata Acquisition

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Domus Romana Exterior - Full Site Side 1
 - Name/Number of Scan 1
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1886
 - Shutter Speed 1/320 - 1/100
 - ISO 100
 - Aperture 11
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Domus Romana Exterior - Full Site Side 2
 - Name/Number of Scan 2
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 2052
 - Shutter Speed 1/320 - 1/200
 - ISO 100 - 160
 - Aperture 11

- Resolution 6000x4000
- Focal Length 24mm

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Monuments
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 2223
 - Shutter Speed 1/200
 - ISO 100
 - Aperture 13
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24

AUTOMATED AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Domus Romana Exterior - Full Site
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 699
 - Shutter Speed 1/4000
 - ISO 200
 - Aperture 1.9
 - Resolution 4096x3072
 - Focal Length 23

MANUAL AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Domus Romana Exterior - Full Site
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 851
 - Shutter Speed 1/160 - 1/80
 - ISO 200 - 1600
 - Aperture 1.8
 - Resolution 7680x4320
 - Focal Length 23

Equipment used in Kleinbardorf

DRONE EQUIPMENT

- DRONE Autel Evo II Dual 640T V3

PHOTOGRAMMETRY EQUIPMENT

Setup 1

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash
- Filter

Setup 2

- Camera Sony A6000
- Lens Sony 16-50mm lens SEL16F28
- Flash
- Filter

Kleinbardorf Paradata Acquisition

AUTOMATED AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 229
 - Shutter Speed 1/400
 - ISO 100
 - Aperture 1.8
 - Resolution 4096x3072
 - Focal Length 23

MANUAL AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 774
 - Shutter Speed 1/320 - 1/60
 - ISO 100 - 400
 - Aperture 1.8
 - Resolution 7680x4320
 - Focal Length 23

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site - Warren
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 5804
 - Shutter Speed 1/320 - 1/160
 - ISO 400 - 640
 - Aperture 5.0 - 8.0
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site - Jacob
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 2669
 - Shutter Speed 1/160 - 1/100
 - ISO 400 - 800
 - Aperture 7.1
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site - Jacob/Aaron
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 2
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1570
 - Shutter Speed 1/125
 - ISO 400 - 500
 - Aperture 7.1
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 16

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Monuments - Warren
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1030

- Shutter Speed 1/250 - 1/160
- ISO 400 - 500
- Aperture 7.1 - 8.0
- Resolution 6000x4000
- Focal Length 24

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Monuments - Jacob
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 410
 - Shutter Speed 1/125
 - ISO 400
 - Aperture 7.1
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 7.1

Equipment used in Unsleben

DRONE EQUIPMENT

- DRONE Autel Evo II Dual 640T V3

PHOTOGRAMMETRY EQUIPMENT

Setup 1

- Camera Sony A6100
- Lens Sony FE F2.8 GMII 24-70mm
- Flash
- Filter

Unsleben Paradata Acquisition

AUTOMATED AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 643
 - Shutter Speed 1/1600
 - ISO 200
 - Aperture 1.8
 - Resolution 4096x3072
 - Focal Length 23

MANUAL AERIAL PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 413
 - Shutter Speed 1/320 - 1/120
 - ISO 200 - 1600
 - Aperture 7.1
 - Resolution 7680x4320
 - Focal Length 24

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site - Jacob
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 868
 - Shutter Speed 1/400 - 1/320
 - ISO 100 - 320
 - Aperture 7.1
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Full Site - Warren
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG
 - Number of Images 1527
 - Shutter Speed 1/320 - 1/160
 - ISO 100
 - Aperture 7.1
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Monuments - Jacob
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG/RAW
 - Number of Images 1224
 - Shutter Speed 1/200
 - ISO 250

- Aperture 5.6
- Resolution 6000x4000
- Focal Length 24

GROUND BASED PHOTOGRAMMETRY PARADATA

- Name of Object Individual Monuments - Warren
 - Name/Number of Scan
 - Camera Setup Used Setup 1
 - Image Format JPEG
 - Number of Images 1039
 - Shutter Speed 1/250 - 1/160
 - ISO 250 - 320
 - Aperture 5.6 - 7.1
 - Resolution 6000x4000
 - Focal Length 24